

Coexisting Kikuchi–Fujimoto Disease and Hashimoto’s Thyroiditis in a Euthyroid Woman. A Case Report and narrative Review

Aus F. Haddad¹ , Jawad K. Haddadin ², Lina Alnaha³ , Nader Hijazi ⁴, Fares H. Haddad⁵

1. Internal Medicine, HULL General Hospital, HULL, GBR

2 Abdali Center for Thyroid Endocrine and Diabetes, Abdali Hospital, AMMAN, JORDAN.

3. Laboratory Department, Abdali Hospital, AMMAN, JORDAN

4. CHEST DIVISION, PRIVATE CLINIC, AMMAN, JORDAN

5. Abdali Center for Thyroid Endocrine and Diabetes, Abdali Hospital, AMMAN, JORDAN.

ABDALI HOSPITAL, AMMAN, JORDAN

Corresponding author:

Fares H. Haddad MD FRCP FACE ,

Abstract

Kikuchi-Fujimoto Disease (KFD) is a self-limited histiocytic necrotizing lymphadenitis that can frequently mimic infection, lymphomas, and, to a lesser degree, autoimmune conditions. Hashimoto thyroiditis (HT) is the commonest autoimmune thyroid disease and is characterized by the presence of anti-thyroid peroxidase antibodies and variable thyroid dysfunction. Although KFD and HT are distinguished anatomically, the coexistence of these diseases can cause diagnostic uncertainty and result in unnecessary extensive laboratory and imaging studies.

Here, we describe a 35-year-old woman with biopsy-confirmed Kikuchi–Fujimoto disease and serologically proven Hashimoto’s autoimmune thyroiditis who presented with fever and tender cervical lymphadenopathy for six months. She was euthyroid yet anti-TPO positive with imaging suggesting thyroiditis. An excisional nodal biopsy showed necrotizing lymphadenitis without neutrophils or plasma cells, thereby establishing the diagnosis of coexisting KFD and HT. She improved with supportive care and surveillance was provided for potential thyroid dysfunction. The awareness of thyroid autoimmune disease and KFD association might reduce unnecessary workup for infection or cancer and allow appropriate evaluation and monitoring for other potential autoimmune diseases, including SLE. The presence of KFD alongside Hashimoto's thyroiditis-and, at times, other autoimmune conditions-warrants a focused thyroid assessment and continued surveillance of autoimmunity

Keywords: autoimmune thyroiditis, hashimoto thyroiditis, histiocytic necrotizing lymphadenitis, kikuchi–fujimoto disease, thyroid peroxidase antibodies

Introduction

Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease (KFD) is a self-limited histiocytic necrotizing lymphadenitis presenting in younger adults as tender cervical lymphadenopathy with fever, often simulating infection or lymphoma [1]. A dysregulated, likely post-viral hyper-immune response has been implicated, particularly in genetically predisposed individuals [2]. Excisional lymph-node biopsy is essential for diagnosis, as fine-needle aspiration is poorly sensitive and imaging can mimic malignancy. Characteristic histology reveals paracortical necrosis with karyorrhectic debris, abundant histiocytes including plasmacytoid dendritic cells, and a paucity of neutrophils and plasma cells [3-5].

Most cases resolve within weeks to months, though recurrence is higher than once appreciated, warranting follow-up [4]. Differentials include tuberculous and suppurative lymphadenitis, lymphoma, lupus lymphadenitis, cat-scratch disease, Sweet's syndrome, Still's disease, and infectious mononucleosis [6]. Cutaneous involvement (facial erythema, erythematous papules or plaques) occurs in 30–40% of cases. KFD and systemic lupus erythematosus (SLE) share a complex relationship and may occur concurrently, sequentially, or independently [6].

Coexisting Hashimoto thyroiditis (HT) further complicates diagnosis; patients may be euthyroid or hypothyroid with elevated anti-TPO antibodies despite normal thyroid function. Since 2018, case syntheses have documented simultaneous or sequential KFD-HT presentations and recommended post-KFD thyroid screening (TSH, free T4, ± ultrasound) [7-11].

We describe here a case of biopsy-confirmed Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease presented by intermittent fever, and tender posterior cervical lymphadenopathy, coexisting with euthyroid Hashimoto thyroiditis (anti-TPO positive). This report is supplemented with a brief review of current literature on KFD-thyroid autoimmunity.

Case Presentation

A 35-year-old Jordanian woman presented with a 6-month history of intermittent high-grade fevers (peaking at 40°C), recurring in self-limited bouts over days to weeks, with associated posterior neck pain, swelling, and fatigue. She denied headaches, cough, chest pain, rhinorrhea, abdominal pain, diarrhea, or rash. Past history included migraine and trigeminal neuralgia; her sister has Hashimoto's thyroiditis. No recent sick contacts, travel, or animal bites were reported.

On admission, she was alert, oriented and in mild distress due to neck swelling. Temperature was high and other vital signs were stable. Examination of cervical lymph nodes revealed bilateral posterior cervical lymphadenopathy more pronounced on right side, with discrete mobile tender nodes and overlying skin shows no erythema or fluctuance. There was no trismus, tonsillar exudate, oropharyngeal lesions, or otologic pathology. Thyroid examination

revealed a slightly diffuse enlarged, firm non-tender thyroid without nodularity or bruit, and no ophthalmopathy or pretibial changes. No axillary or inguinal lymphadenopathy was detected. Abdominal, chest and cardiac examinations were unremarkable.

Initial laboratory evaluation showed a normal complete blood count with mildly elevated ESR (25 mm/h) and markedly raised CRP (27.64 mg/L), indicating systemic inflammation without cytopenia or leukocytosis. Liver biochemistry demonstrated a hepatocellular pattern of injury with preserved total protein, albumin, globulin; the lipid profile was unremarkable and ferritin was modestly elevated. Extensive infectious screening was negative, α -fetoprotein was normal. Autoimmune studies revealed a borderline speckled ANA titre of 1:80 with negative rheumatoid factor, antismooth muscle and antimitochondrial antibodies. Thyroid investigations showed biochemical euthyroidism with elevated thyroglobulin antibodies (12 IU/mL) and anti-TPO antibodies (115 IU/mL), TRAb 1.1 IU/ML (<1.5) consistent with underlying autoimmune (Hashimoto) thyroiditis. (Table 1)

Category	Test	Patient Value	Units	Normal Range
Full Blood Count	Hemoglobin	13.4	g/dL	M: 13–18 / F: 12–16
	Hematocrit	42.3	%	M: 40–52 / F: 36–48
	RBC	4.8	$\times 10^6/\mu\text{L}$	M: 4.5–5.9 / F: 4.1–5.1
	WBC	5.9	$\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$	4.5–11.0
	Platelets	233	$\times 10^3/\mu\text{L}$	150–400
	MCV	88.6	fL	80–100
	MCH	28.1	pg	27–33
	MCHC	31.7	g/dL	32–36
	RDW	14.8	%	11.5–15.0
	Liver Function	ALT	102	U/L
AST		53	U/L	10–45
GGT		55	U/L	M: <60 / F: <40
ALP		70	U/L	30–130
Total Bilirubin		0.2	mg/dL	0.3–1.2
Direct Bilirubin		0.1	mg/dL	0–0.3
Albumin		4.0	g/dL	3.5–5.5
Total Protein	6.3	g/dL	6.0–8.3	

Electrolytes & Renal	Magnesium	1.8	mg/dL	1.7–2.2
	Sodium	140	mmol/L	136–146
	Potassium	3.4	mmol/L	3.5–5.1
	Chloride	106	mmol/L	98–106
	eGFR	116	mL/min/1.73m ²	≥60
Inflammation	CRP	2.3	mg/L	<5.0
	ESR	25	mm/hr	M: <15 / F: <20
	Ferritin	172	µg/L	M: 12–300 / F: 10–150
Thyroid	TSH	2.160	mU/L	0.45–4.00
	TSH Receptor Ab (TRAb)	1.1	IU/mL	<1.75
Autoimmune (ANA Panel)	ANA	1/80 (Speckled)	Titer	Negative / <1:40
	RNP/Sm	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	SS-A (Ro)	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	SS-B (La)	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	PM-Scl	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Centromere B	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	dsDNA	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Histones	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Sm	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Ro-52 recombinant	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Scl-70	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Jo-1	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	PCNA	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Nucleosomes	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	Rib-P-Protein	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
	AMA-M2	Negative	Qualitative	Negative
Other Autoimmune	ASMA	<1/20	Titer	Negative / <1:20
	AMA	<1/20	Titer	Negative / <1:20

Tumor / Infectious Screen	AFP	2.6	µg/L	0.6–6.6
	CMV IgM	0.18	COI	<1.0 (negative)
	HCV Ab	0.04	COI	<1.0 (negative)
	HBsAg	0.35	COI	<1.0 (negative)
Lipids	Total Cholesterol	186	mg/dL	<200 (desirable)
	Triglycerides	79	mg/dL	<150
	HDL	41	mg/dL	M: >40 / F: >50
	LDL	127	mg/dL	<130 (optimal <100)
Vitamins	Vitamin D	115.5	nmol/L	75–200 (optimal)
	Vitamin B12	582.1	pmol/L	148–590
Urinalysis	Urine WBC	48	/HPF	<5
	Urine RBC	10	/HPF	<3–5

Neck ultrasound(figures1a+b) was performed and showed bilaterally enlarged cervical and submandibular lymph nodes, more pronounced on right side, with loss of fatty hilum. Thyroid U/S showed bulky thyroid lobes and isthmus, with homogenous increased color Doppler flow vascularity, suggested of thyroiditis confirmed by laboratory investigations(figure a1,a2,a3) Moreover, CT scan with contrast of neck/chest/abdomen/pelvis revealed multiple enlarged cervical/submandibular lymph nodes without thoracic or abdominopelvic masses (figure 1: b1, b2). Similarly, MRI scan showed multiple bilateral enlarged cervical lymph nodes, Right side > Left side, with no other soft tissue masses.

FIGURE 1: thyroid ultrasound and neckCT scan Figure 1a :Thyroid U/S showed bulky both thyroid lobes and isthmus, with homogenous increased color Doppler flow vascularity, suggested of thyroiditis(a1,a2) and bilaterally enlarged cervical and submandibular lymph nodes, more pronounced on right side(a3)

Figure 1:b1,b2;

CT scan with contrast of neck revealed multiple enlarged cervical/submandibular lymph.

Similarly Right side (b1) > Left side(b2) .

FIGURE 2: Kikuchi–Fujimoto lymphadenitis pathology Figure 2. Kikuchi–Fujimoto lymphadenitis pathology (H&E); (A): Low-power view showing distorted lymph-node architecture with geographic, pale necrotizing foci (black arrow), (B): Residual reactive germinal centers with a sharp interface between the pale necrotizing zones and surrounding lymphoid tissue (arrows) and (C): Pale areas composed of karyorrhectic debris with numerous histiocytes (including plasmacytoid/monocytic forms) admixed with lymphocytes; typical paucity of neutrophils

Excisional cervical lymph node biopsy showed distorted architecture with large pale paracortical zones (Figure 2a), reactive germinal centers, and hyperplasia of the interfollicular and paracortical zones (Figure 2b). These zones contained well-circumscribed necrotizing foci with karyorrhectic debris, histiocytes, and plasmacytoid monocytes (Figure 2c). Neutrophils and plasma cells were absent to rare, with no granulomas, caseous necrosis, or features of malignancy. Ziehl-Neelsen and PAS-diastase stains were negative. Flow cytometry was not performed on this excisional biopsy.

Given the patient’s preserved overall condition and euthyroid status, management was conservative. She received Paracetamol 1g every 8 hours and Ibuprofen 400mg every 8 hours for fever and pain, with a short trial of Morphine 5mg p.o. every 6–8 hours for severe cervical pain, with no notable side effects. No antibiotics, corticosteroids, or immunosuppressants were given. Fever and lymphadenopathy gradually resolved. Thyroid levels were monitored and remained biochemically euthyroid throughout follow-up, with no levothyroxine required.

Informed verbal consent was obtained from patient herself .

Discussion

Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease (KFD) is a rare, self-limiting, benign necrotizing lymphadenitis that can lead to misdiagnosis and misdirected empiric therapies [6,12,13]. In this case, high-grade relapsing fever, tender posterior cervical lymphadenopathy, and hepatocellular transaminitis without markers of infection or neoplasm created a diagnostic picture easily confused with occult infection, autoimmune hepatitis, or lymphoma. Excisional lymph node biopsy was crucial: histopathology showed paracortical necrosis, karyorrhectic debris, abundant histiocytes and plasmacytoid dendritic cells, with absent neutrophils and plasma cells, effectively ruling out suppurative bacterial lymphadenitis, tuberculosis, and lymphoma. Negative Ziehl-Neelsen and PAS staining, unremarkable infectious serology, and the absence of high-titre autoantibodies — alongside anti-TPO positivity — crystallized the diagnosis and averted unnecessary antituberculosis or broad-spectrum antibiotic therapy. This highlights that KFD should be actively considered in the differential diagnosis of necrotizing lymphadenitis in young women, including non-East Asian populations. Concurrent biopsy-confirmed KFD and serologically proven autoimmune thyroiditis in a euthyroid patient further supports KFD's expanding autoimmune spectrum; the coexistence of Hashimoto thyroiditis may reflect ongoing dysregulated cell-mediated immunity warranting prolonged surveillance for thyroid dysfunction and other autoimmune comorbidities [14].

This case supports a conservative, symptom-oriented approach in stable patients. Despite debilitating neck pain requiring short-term opioids alongside paracetamol and ibuprofen, the case self-resolved without corticosteroids, antibiotics, or immunosuppressants — reinforcing that systemic steroids should be reserved for life-threatening organ involvement, severe constitutional symptoms, or associated systemic autoimmunity [14]. A correct KFD diagnosis avoids the psychological and medical consequences of misdiagnosed malignancy, and long-term follow-up remains vital for detecting relapse or progression of thyroid autoimmune disease. A literature review using the keywords thyroid peroxidase antibodies, kikuchi-fujimoto disease, histiocytic necrotizing lymphadenitis, Hashimoto thyroiditis and autoimmune thyroiditis was performed without time interval limits. Among 11 documented KFD-HT cases, the overwhelming majority were young women aged 12–43 years, with only one male case [15]. All presented with painful cervical lymphadenopathy and fever; a minority had rash or other constitutional/neurological symptoms. Lymphadenopathy was typically unilateral and right-sided, though bilateral and axillary involvement are reported [16], consistent with our case of a 35-year-old woman with bilateral posterior cervical lymphadenopathy.

The temporal relationship between KFD and HT is heterogeneous: KFD followed HT in some cases [7,11,16,17], HT followed KFD in others [9,18,19], and both occurred simultaneously in four reports [8,10,15,20]. Our case involved concurrent diagnosis, suggesting HT may emerge

during febrile lymphadenopathy investigation rather than being clinically antecedent. Thyroid functional status varied across reported cases — hypothyroid, euthyroid, and hyperthyroid — with our patient fitting the subgroup in which HT is immunologically active but biochemically silent [18]. Therapeutic approaches ranged from NSAIDs alone [17,18] to systemic corticosteroids [9-11] and broader immunosuppression where SLE or RA/T1DM coexisted. In our case, conservative management with acetaminophen, ibuprofen, and short-term opioid analgesia achieved complete resolution. Thyroid hormone replacement and immunosuppression should be reserved for significant endocrine dysregulation or additional systemic autoimmune disease. A summary of literature findings is shown in Table 2.

Study	Location	Age/Sex	Other Coexisting conditions	Onset	Presentation	Thyroid status (euthyroid/hypo-/hashitoxicosis)	Treatment
Aqel et al. 1997 [16]	Saudi Arabia	43/F	Mixed Connective tissue disorder (MCTD)	KFD after 31 months of HT diagnosis	Fever and bilateral enlarged axillary lymph nodes	Hypothyroid	Hemithyroidectomy then 0.1 mg thyroxin daily
Azzam et al. 2023 [20]	UAE	12/F	No other conditions	Simultaneous KFD and HT	Bilateral painful tender cervical LNs, fever (peaking 39.5°C) and erythematous skin rash	Hypothyroid	L-Thyroxin 25 mcg once daily + NSAIDs
Bazkke et al. 2022 [11]	Syria	36/F	Pregnant	KFD after years of HT diagnosis	Painful tender unilateral (Right side) enlarged cervical LNs, high grade fever, rigors and difficulty moving right arm	Not reported	Corticosteroids for 20 days
Choi et al. 2016 [15]	South Korea	32/M	Sporadic medullary microcarcinoma 2 months after resolution of KFD	Simultaneous KFD and HT	Painful tender unilateral (Right side) enlarged cervical LNs, High grade fever (peaking 38.5°C), chills and malaise.	Hypothyroid	levothyroxine 100 µg/day + supportive care for
Dinh et al. 2025 [8]	Vietnam	16/F	No other conditions	Simultaneous KFD and HT	Fever episodes for three months, unilateral (Left side) enlarged painful tender cervical LNs, fatigue, anorexia and weight loss	Hypothyroid	Levothyroxin + NSAIDs
Go et al. 2012 [10]	South Korea	17/F	Iron Deficiency anemia	Simultaneous KFD and HT	Multiple unilateral (Right side) painful tender enlarged cervical LNs + tender goiter	Euthyroid	Oral prednisolone (0.5 mg/kg/day)
Lee et al. 2018 [9]	South Korea	16/F	No other conditions	HT after KFD	Multiple bilateral (Right side > Left side) painful tender enlarged cervical LNs (3	Euthyroid	oral prednisolone (1 mg/kg/day)

					weeks) + fever (1 week)		
Rubio SI et al 1996 [18]	USA	27/F	No other conditions	HT 2 months after KFD	Bilateral cervical lymphadenopathy and fever	Hyperthyroid	NSAIDs for KFD and propranolol 20mg three times daily for tachycardia
Saratziotis et al. 2012 [17]	Greece	19/F	No other conditions	KFD after hx of HT	Enlarged painful tender right anterior cervical LNs, fever (up to 38.5°C) and chills	Euthyroid	Supportive treatment
Shahrokh et al. 2022 [7]	USA	30/F	RA, T1DM and Anemia of chronic disease	KFD after hx of HT	A generalized tonic-clonic seizure after days of Right axillary Lymphadenopathy, low grade fever and chills	Euthyroid	Insulin regimen and oral ferritin
Sharma et al. 2020 [19]	Kenya	29/F	SLE	HT 2 months after KFD	Headache and fever for 5 days + Significantly enlarged cervical LNs	Hypothyroid	Antipyretic, prednisolone, azathioprine and hydroxychloroquine

TABLE 2: Brief review of co-occurred cases of Kikuchi syndrome and Hashimoto’s thyroiditis

KFD, Kikuchi–Fujimoto disease;

HT, Hashimoto thyroiditis; MCTD, mixed connective tissue disease; LN(s), lymph node(s); RA, rheumatoid arthritis; SLE, systemic lupus erythematosus; T1DM, type 1 diabetes mellitus; NSAIDs, non-steroidal anti-inflammatory drugs; hx, history.

Conclusions

The current case delineates the unique instances of simultaneous biopsy-confirmed Kikuchi–Fujimoto disease and serologically proven Hashimoto’s autoimmune thyroiditis in a euthyroid young female patient with a constellation of symptoms comprising of prolonged fever, transaminitis, and cervical lymphadenopathy.

To establish the diagnosis and to avert unwarranted antimicrobial and/or immunosuppressive treatment, an excisional lymph node biopsy is highly advisable. This case is consistent with other published works, advocate the conservative approach with symptoms management paradigm and the selective assessment for thyroid autoimmunity and monitored follow-up.

We recommend an interval thyroid function monitoring plan and symptom triggers for autoimmune reassessment and repeat of some autoantibodies (ana) to clarify incomplete SLE

Limitations ;some new tests for TB and other antibodies were not available at tin=me of admission that might affect the diagnosis .Longer term of follow up was not possible as the patient was missed from follow up

References

1. Hutchinson CB, Wang E: Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease. *Arch Pathol Lab Med.* 2010, 134:289-93. 10.5858/134.2.289
2. Deb A, Fernandez V, Kilinc E, et al.: Kikuchi-Fujimoto Disease: A Case Series and Review of the Literature. *Diseases.* 2024, 12:271. 10.3390/diseases12110271
3. Gism Elseed I, Osman H, Ahmedfiqi O, Najmi F, Al-Hebshi A: Kikuchi-Fujimoto Disease: A Rare Benign Cause of Lymphadenopathy That Mimics Malignant Lymphoma. *Cureus.* 2022, 14:23177. 10.7759/cureus.23177
4. Srikantharajah M, Mahendra P, Vydianath B, Lowe GC: Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease: a rare but important differential diagnosis for lymphadenopathy. *BMJ Case Rep.* 2014:2014205470. 10.1136/bcr-2014-205470
5. Osborn M, Aqel N, Levine TS. The fine needle aspiration appearances of Kikuchi's lymphadenitis. *Cytopathology.* 2009 Feb;20(1):36-43. doi: 10.1111/j.1365-2303.2007.00491.x. Epub 2007 Oct 4. PMID: 17916091.
6. Mahajan VK, Sharma V, Sharma N, Rani R: Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease: A comprehensive review. *World J Clin Cases.* 2023, 11:3664-79. 10.12998/wjcc.v11.i16.3664
7. Shahrokh S, Hasan A, Alim S, Hebert M, Rizvi K: Kikuchi-Fujimoto Disease Complicated by Rheumatoid Arthritis, Type 1 Diabetes Mellitus, and Hypothyroidism. *Cureus .* 2022, 14(1):e21008. 10.7759/cureus.21008
8. Cao Dinh H, Doan DM, Tran KQ, Tran TT, Nguyen SL: Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease co-occurring with Hashimoto thyroiditis: A case report and literature review. *Ann Clin Biochem.* 2025, 62:75-80. 10.1177/00045632241280595
9. Lee EJ, Lee HS, Park JE, Hwang JS: Association Kikuchi disease with Hashimoto thyroiditis: a case report and literature review. *Ann Pediatr Endocrinol Metab.* 2018, 23:99-102. 10.6065/apem.2018.23.2.99
10. Go EJ, Jung YJ, Han SB, Suh BK, Kang JH: A case of Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease with autoimmune thyroiditis . *Korean J Pediatr.* 2012, 55:445. 10.3345/kjp.2012.55.11.445
11. Bazkke B, Osman J, Shahrour M, et al.: A pregnant women with history of hashimoto's thyroiditis diagnosed with Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease: the first case report. *Thyroid Res.* 2022, 15:16. 10.1186/s13044-022-00135-3

12. Bosch X, Guilabert A, Miquel R, Campo E: Enigmatic Kikuchi-Fujimoto disease: a comprehensive review . *Am J Clin Pathol.* 2004, 122:141-52. 10.1309/YF08-1L4T-KYWV-YVPQ
13. Song Y, Liu S, Song L, et al : Histiocytic Necrotizing Lymphadenitis (Kikuchi-Fujimoto Disease) Concurrent With Aseptic Meningitis. . *Front. Neurol.* 12:565387. doi:10.3389/fneur.2021.565387. 2021 Apr, 12:565387:10.3389/fneur.2021.565387
14. Song Y, Liu S, Song L, Chen H, Bai M, Yan J, Luo T, Liu K, Sun L, Zhao Y.: Case Report: Histiocytic Necrotizing Lymphadenitis (Kikuchi-Fujimoto Disease) Concurrent With Aseptic Meningitis.. *Front Neurol.* 2021 Apr 20;doi: 10.3389/fneur.2021.565387. PMID: 33959084; PMCID: PMC8093430.. 2021 Apr, 12:565387. 10.3389/fneur.2021.565387
15. Choi MR, Yoo SB, Kim JH: Sporadic medullary microcarcinoma in a male patient with concurrent Hashimoto's hypothyroidism and Kikuchi disease. *Korean J Intern Med.* 2016, 31:1184-6. 10.3904/kjim.2014.395
16. Aqel NM, Amr SS, Najjar MM, Henry K: Kikuchi's lymphadenitis developing in a patient with mixed connective tissue disease and Hashimoto's thyroiditis. *Br J Rheumatol.* 1997, 36:1236-8. 10.1093/oxfordjournals.rheumatology.a031439
17. Saratziotis A, Karakousis K, Tzika K, Oikonomou KG, Vlachostergios PJ: Hashimoto's Thyroiditis and Kikuchi's Disease: Presentation of a Case and Review of the Literature. *Case Reports in Otolaryngology.* 2012:1-5. 10.1155/2012/267595
18. Rubio SI, Plewinsky TS, Sabatini M, Poretsky L: Kikuchi's disease associated with Hashimoto's thyroiditis . *J Endocrinol Invest.* 1996, 19:136-7. <http://10.1007/BF03349850>
19. Sharma A, Kroumpouzou G, Kassir M, et al.: Rosacea management: A comprehensive review. *J Cosmet Dermatol.* 2022, 21:1895-904. 10.1111/jocd.14816 7 of 8
20. Azzam M, Helali H, Sharif E, et al. : Kikuchi Disease in Children: A Report of Two Cases. . *Cureus.* 2023, 15(2):e35160. doi.org/10.7759/cureus.35160

Additional Information

Author Contributions All authors have reviewed the final version to be published and agreed to be accountable for all aspects of the work.

Concept and design: Fares H. Haddad , Jawad K. Haddadin , Aus F. Haddad

Acquisition, analysis, or interpretation of data: Fares H. Haddad , Jawad K. Haddadin , Aus F. Haddad, Lina Alnahr , Nader Hijazi

Drafting of the manuscript: Fares H. Haddad , Jawad K. Haddadin , Aus F. Haddad, Lina Alnahr , Nader Hijazi

Critical review of the manuscript for important intellectual content: Fares H. Haddad , Jawad K. Haddadin , Aus F. Haddad, Lina Alnahr , Nader Hijazi

Supervision: Fares H. Haddad , Aus F. Haddad

Disclosures

Human subjects: Informed consent for treatment and open access publication was obtained or waived by all participants in this study. Non required issued approval --. informed verbal consent was obtained from patient herself . "IRB approval: Not applicable

Conflicts of interest: In compliance with the ICMJE uniform disclosure form, all authors declare the following: Payment/services info: All authors have declared that no financial support was received from any organization for the submitted work.

Financial relationships: All authors have declared that they have no financial relationships at present or within the previous three years with any organizations that might have an interest in the submitted work.

Other relationships: All authors have declared that there are no other relationships or activities that could appear to have influenced the submitted work.

The authors declare that generative artificial intelligence (AI) tools (ChatGPT, OpenAI) were used to assist in language refinement and grammar checking during the preparation of this manuscript. The authors reviewed and verified all content, and they take full responsibility for the integrity and accuracy of the manuscript."